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Histological Studies on the Spleen of Emu (*Dromaius novaehollandiae*)

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ABSTRACT

The spleen was enclosed in a thick connective tissue capsule and it consists of outer and inner layers. From the capsule small trabeculae with large blood vessels pass into the parenchyma of spleen. The parenchyma not differentiate into red pulp and white pulp. The white pulp was seen as diffuse areas of lymphoid tissue enveloping central arteries. Germinal centers were observed. Sheathed capillaries were also observed in the red pulp. Red pulp was composed of loose spongy tissue arranged into anastomosing splenic cords separated by venous sinuses. Within the cell cords lymphocytes, macrophages, erythrocytes and few plasma cells were observed.

Keywords: Emu, Spleen, Histology

Being primary blood forming organ in embryonic life spleen is an important organ in all vertebrates. In the adult fowl Mjassojedoff (1926) found the spleen to be predominantly a lymphocyte producing organ. Its importance in disease resistance is presumably accentuated by the scarcity of avian lymph nodes. Though a lot of research work has been done on the spleen of the many avian species but the information on the spleen of the emu was found to be meager. Hence the present study was undertaken.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Six adult emu birds irrespective of the sex and age were utilized for the present study. The birds were slaughtered for commercial purpose and the tissue pieces were collected from the spleen. The tissue pieces were processed for paraffin sections of 5-6 microns thickness. Sections were subjected to routine as well as special staining methods like Van Gieson's for collagen fibers, Gomori's method for reticular fibres and

Weigert's method for elastic fibers (Singh and Sulochana, 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The spleen was enclosed by a thick fibrous connective tissue capsule in concurrence with the Venkatesan et al, (2005) in Japanese quail and Hodges (1974) in fowl. Two main zones were observed in the capsule an outer zone composed of collagen fibers predominantly and a few elastic fibers accounting about one third of the total thickness and an inner zone, composed mainly of reticular fibers, elastic fibers, fine collagen fibers and smooth muscle fibres. This zone was accounting about two third of the thickness (Fig. 1). Small trabeculae composed of collagen, elastic and smooth muscle fibres and blood vessels entered in to the parenchyma of spleen (Fig.1) as observed by Indu et al, (2008) in white pekin ducks and Nasu T. et al, (1992) in doves. This finding was in contrary to the reports of Hodges (1974) in fowl. The parenchyma was

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Fig. 1: Photomicrography of spleen of Emu bird showing outer zone of capsule (OZ), Inner zone of capsule (IZ) and Traft capsule (TR)

H & E x 40

not differentiated into red pulp and white pulp as in the mammalian spleen. The underlying frame work of the splenic parenchyma consisted of reticular fibers. The reticular cells, lymphoblasts, lymphocytes, heterophills and macrophages were the cellular populations in the splenic parenchyma. These are in agreement with the findings of Nasu-T et al, (1992) in doves, Venkatesan et al., (2005) in Japanese quail Indu et al, (2008) in white pekin birds.

Within the splenic parenchyma the medium sized or small branches of splenic arteries were surrounded by sheaths of mainly lymphoid tissue and reticular cells and, white pulp (Fig.2). Germinal centers

Fig. 2: Photomicrography of spleen of Emu bird showing white pulp (WP) and Red Pulp (RP) and sheathed Arteries (SA)

H & E x 100

were located near the central arteries. The central arteries were eccentric to the germinal centers and they form pulp arteries (Fig.3) which in turn continued as pulp arteriole, and terminated in two or more capillaries in the marginal zone. The ellipsoids (pericapillary macrophage sheath) were observed in the marginal zone as observed by Venkatesan et al, (2005) in Japanese quail and Indu et al. (2008) in white pekin ducks.

The red pulp was made of loose spongy tissue arranged as cellular cords surrounded by venous sinuses (Fig.3). Sheathed capillaries were found in the red pulp also (Fig.3). This observation leads to the belief that the ellipsoidal sheath and its surrounding macrophages might be the structure which is functional equivalent to the mammalian marginal zone as reported by the Jeurissen and Janse (1994) in fowl, Venkatesan et al, (2005) in Japanese quail. The venous sinuses are irregular passages within the red pulp lined by flattened and elongated endothelial cells. The cell cords constituted delicate network of reticular cells with their

Fig. 3: Photomicrography of spleen of Emu bird showing white pulp (WP) and Red Pulp (RP) sheathed capillary (SI) and Pulp Artery (PA)

H & E x 400

process running in all directions uniting one cell to other. Lymphocytes, erythrocytes, macrophages, eosinophils, and very few plasma cells were observed. These are in total agreement with the Hodges (1974) in fowl, Venkatesan et al, (2005) in Japanese quail and Indu et al, (2008) in white pekin ducks.

REFERENCES

- Hodges, R.D. 1974. The Histology of the Domestic Fowl. Academic press, London, pp: 88-100.
- Indu, V. R.; Chungath, J. J.; Harshan, K. R.; Ashok, N.; Lucy, K.M. and Biju, S. 2008. Gross and Histological Studies on the Spleen of white pekin ducks. Ind.Vet. J.85 :61-63.
- Jeurissen, S.H.M and Janse, E.M.1994. Functional definition of marginal zone in the chicken spleen. Pergmon press, Paris. pp:198-210.
- Mjassojedott, S.W. 1926. Die Zellformen des Bindegewefes und des Blutes und die Blutbildung beim Erwachsenen Hulin. Folia . Haemat. 32: 263-296.
- Nasu-J, S., and Nakai, M.1992. Morphological study of the dove spleen. Poultry Science 71. pp: 1527.
- Singh ,U.B. and Sulochana, S. 1997. Handbook of Histological and Histochemical Techniques. Premier Publishing House. Hyderabad, pp: 1-111
- Venkatesan, S.,; Geetha ramesh and Vijayaragavan, C. 2005. Age related changes in Histomorphology of the Spleen of the Japanese quail Ind.J.Vet.Anat.17(1&2):19-23.

